

Additional results for hypothesis testing analyses to understand functional responses of greater sage-grouse space use in response to catastrophic wildfire.

Table S1. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of sagebrush cover around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results show relaxed use and selection of sagebrush cover, often demonstrated by specialist species, with strongest use and selection at low availability that approaches proportional use and selection at high availability. These functional response results are also consistent across observational scales, but strongest at finest scale.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Transect	3.09	2.57-3.61	0.10	-0.07-0.27	26.60	21.61-31.59	0.14	-0.08-0.36
100	1.47	0.73-2.21	0.55	0.27-0.83	8.68	3.12-14.24	0.68	0.35-1.00
200	1.41	0.61-2.20	0.56	0.26-0.86	8.33	2.76-13.90	0.68	0.35-1.00
300	1.40	0.59-2.21	0.56	0.26-0.87	8.27	2.68-13.85	0.68	0.35-1.00
400	1.40	0.58-2.21	0.56	0.26-0.87	8.25	2.62-13.87	0.67	0.35-1.00
500	1.38	0.56-2.19	0.57	0.26-0.87	8.19	2.55-13.83	0.67	0.34-1.00
600	1.36	0.52-2.18	0.58	0.26-0.89	8.08	2.38-13.77	0.68	0.35-1.01
700	1.34	0.50-2.17	0.58	0.27-0.90	8.00	2.32-13.67	0.68	0.35-1.01
800	1.32	0.50-2.15	0.58	0.27-0.90	7.92	2.32-13.53	0.68	0.35-1.01
900	1.32	0.51-2.15	0.58	0.28-0.89	7.91	2.36-13.48	0.68	0.36-1.00
1000	1.33	0.52-2.15	0.58	0.27-0.89	7.92	2.37-13.47	0.68	0.36-1.00

Figure S1. Plot of log of mean cover at used sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, at the scale of 30 m around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates relaxed selection of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S2. Plot of log of mean cover at used sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates relaxed selection of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse that is consistent across spatial scales.

Figure S3. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, at the scale of 30 m around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates consistent use of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, regardless of available cover.

Figure S4. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates greater sage-grouse used greater sagebrush cover than was available when availability was low (approximately < 20%) but used sagebrush cover in proportion to its availability when greater cover was available on the landscape. This was consistent across scales.

Table S2. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of total shrub cover around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results show evidence of functional responses at fine scales (≤ 100 m), with disproportionate use and selection of shrub cover at low availability, but weak evidence of functional responses at scales > 100 m.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Transect	2.67	1.17-4.18	0.30	-0.14-0.74	29.11	10.19-48.04	0.38	-0.21-0.98
100	1.33	0.19-2.48	0.61	0.23-1.00	9.41	0.90-17.91	0.72	0.33-1.12
200	1.28	0.05-2.51	0.62	0.21-1.04	8.86	0.25-17.47	0.73	0.33-1.12
300	1.29	0.04-2.54	0.62	0.20-1.04	8.87	0.17-17.58	0.72	0.32-1.12
400	1.30	0.06-2.54	0.62	0.20-1.03	8.96	0.23-17.69	0.71	0.31-1.11
500	1.28	0.03-2.52	0.62	0.20-1.04	8.88	0.17-17.58	0.71	0.31-1.11
600	1.24	-0.02-2.5	0.63	0.21-1.06	8.68	-0.03-17.39	0.72	0.32-1.12
700	1.21	-0.05-2.46	0.64	0.22-1.06	8.46	-0.12-17.05	0.73	0.34-1.12
800	1.19	-0.04-2.42	0.65	0.23-1.06	8.33	-0.08-16.74	0.74	0.35-1.12
900	1.19	-0.03-2.41	0.65	0.24-1.06	8.31	0.00-16.62	0.74	0.35-1.12
1000	1.20	-0.02-2.42	0.65	0.23-1.06	8.33	0.06-16.61	0.73	0.35-1.11

Figure S5. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of total shrub cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, at the scale of 30 m around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates relaxed selection of total shrub cover by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S6. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of total shrub cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates relaxed selection of shrub cover by nesting greater sage-grouse at 100 m. Results at scales > 100 m failed to reject the null hypothesis of no functional response but were visually similar to the results at the 100-m scale.

Figure S7. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of total shrub cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, at the scale of 30 m around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates greater sage-grouse used greater shrub cover than was available when availability was low (approximately < 35%) but used shrub cover in proportion to its availability when greater shrub cover was available on the landscape.

Figure S8. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of total shrub cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). Results at these scales failed to reject the null hypothesis of no functional response but were visually similar to the results at the 30-m scale, where a functional response was detected.

Table S3. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of Simpson’s diversity index of sagebrush cover classes around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results show a consistent tradeoff functional response at extents > 100 m, with greater selection and use of heterogeneous patches (with respect to sagebrush cover) in more homogeneous landscapes, and selection and use of patches that are with more homogeneous sagebrush cover in landscapes with more heterogeneity. These functional response results are consistent across observational scales >100 m.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
100	-1.06	-2.24-0.12	0.30	-0.49-1.1	0.16	-0.04-0.36	0.31	-0.52-1.14
200	-0.88	-1.63 - -0.14	0.33	-0.24-0.90	0.19	0.01-0.36	0.31	-0.28-0.91
300	-0.89	-1.50 - -0.28	0.29	-0.21-0.79	0.21	0.06-0.37	0.25	-0.25-0.75
400	-0.94	-1.43 - -0.44	0.23	-0.19-0.65	0.25	0.11-0.38	0.18	-0.23-0.59
500	-0.91	-1.33 - -0.48	0.21	-0.17-0.58	0.27	0.14-0.40	0.16	-0.21-0.53
600	-0.88	-1.28 - -0.48	0.21	-0.15-0.56	0.27	0.14-0.40	0.17	-0.19-0.53
700	-0.86	-1.27 - -0.46	0.21	-0.16-0.58	0.28	0.14-0.42	0.17	-0.20-0.54
800	-0.85	-1.29 - -0.42	0.20	-0.21-0.61	0.29	0.14-0.45	0.15	-0.25-0.55
900	-0.85	-1.30 - -0.39	0.20	-0.24-0.64	0.30	0.14-0.46	0.14	-0.27-0.56
1000	-0.83	-1.30 - -0.36	0.21	-0.25-0.67	0.30	0.13-0.47	0.14	-0.28-0.57

Figure S9. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of Simpson's diversity index of sagebrush cover categories by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates tradeoff selection of heterogeneous patches of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse at scales > 100 m. Results at the 100-m scale failed to reject the null hypothesis of no functional response but were visually similar to the results at larger scales.

Figure S10. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of Simpson's diversity index of sagebrush cover categories by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates tradeoffs in use of heterogeneous patches of sagebrush cover by nesting greater sage-grouse at scales > 100 m. Results at the 100-m scale failed to reject the null hypothesis of no functional response but were visually similar to the results at larger scales.

Table S4. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of sagebrush height around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results show relaxed use and selection of sagebrush heights, often with strongest use and selection of taller sagebrush when shorter sagebrush is more available, but where use and selection approaches proportional when taller sagebrush is more available. These functional response results are consistent across observational scales ≥ 100 m.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Transect	1.41	0.07-2.74	0.67	0.32-1.02	18.78	0.18-37.37	0.75	0.35-1.15
100	1.79	1.13-2.45	0.54	0.34-0.73	17.14	9.24-25.04	0.65	0.43-0.87
200	1.69	0.98-2.40	0.56	0.35-0.77	16.26	8.06-24.46	0.66	0.43-0.89
300	1.66	0.93-2.40	0.57	0.36-0.79	15.99	7.71-24.26	0.67	0.44-0.90
400	1.65	0.91-2.38	0.58	0.36-0.79	15.87	7.59-24.16	0.67	0.44-0.90
500	1.62	0.89-2.36	0.58	0.36-0.80	15.72	7.42-24.02	0.68	0.44-0.91
600	1.59	0.84-2.33	0.59	0.37-0.81	15.41	7.05-23.77	0.68	0.45-0.92
700	1.56	0.82-2.31	0.60	0.38-0.82	15.18	6.81-23.56	0.69	0.45-0.92
800	1.56	0.81-2.31	0.60	0.38-0.82	15.07	6.72-23.42	0.69	0.46-0.93
900	1.56	0.81-2.31	0.60	0.38-0.82	15.08	6.76-23.40	0.69	0.46-0.92
1000	1.56	0.82-2.31	0.60	0.38-0.82	15.07	6.74-23.41	0.69	0.45-0.92

Figure S11. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush height by nesting greater sage-grouse, at the scale of 30 m around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to reject the null hypothesis of no functional response in selection at this spatial scale.

Figure S12. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush height by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates relaxed selection of patches with taller sagebrush by nesting greater sage-grouse at scales ≥ 100 m.

Figure S13. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of sagebrush height by nesting greater sage-grouse, at the scale of 30 m around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to reject the null hypothesis of no functional response in use at this spatial scale.

Figure S14. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush height by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates disproportionate use of patches with taller sagebrush by nesting greater sage-grouse when shorter sagebrush (approximately < 40 cm) was more available, but proportional use of sagebrush heights when taller sagebrush was more available.

Table S5. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of total herbaceous cover around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results failed to detect evidence of functional responses in use or selection at any spatial scale.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
100	0.76	-0.09-1.60	0.77	0.49-1.05	5.29	-1.06-11.62	0.81	0.51-1.11
200	0.77	-0.06-1.60	0.77	0.49-1.05	5.55	-0.71-11.81	0.81	0.51-1.11
300	0.82	-0.11-1.75	0.75	0.45-1.06	5.97	-0.84-12.77	0.79	0.46-1.11
400	0.85	-0.14-1.84	0.74	0.41-1.07	6.19	-1.05-13.43	0.77	0.43-1.12
500	0.90	-0.14-1.94	0.73	0.38-1.07	6.51	-1.02-14.05	0.76	0.40-1.11
600	0.92	-0.11-1.96	0.72	0.37-1.06	6.64	-0.89-14.18	0.75	0.39-1.11
700	0.94	-0.10-1.98	0.71	0.37-1.06	6.73	-0.80-14.26	0.74	0.39-1.10
800	0.98	-0.05-2.00	0.70	0.36-1.04	6.93	-0.52-14.38	0.74	0.38-1.09
900	1.00	-0.01-2.01	0.69	0.36-1.03	7.07	-0.28-14.41	0.73	0.38-1.08
1000	1.03	0.02-2.03	0.68	0.35-1.02	7.23	-0.09-14.55	0.72	0.38-1.07

Figure S15. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of total herbaceous cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect evidence of functional responses in selection at any spatial scale.

Figure S16. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in selection of total herbaceous cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect evidence of functional responses in use at any spatial scale.

Table S6. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of perennial herbaceous cover around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results failed to detect evidence of functional responses in use or selection at any spatial scale.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
100	0.78	-0.07-1.63	0.76	0.47-1.05	5.22	-0.88-11.33	0.80	0.50-1.11
200	0.77	-0.07-1.60	0.77	0.49-1.05	5.23	-0.78-11.24	0.81	0.51-1.12
300	0.81	-0.10-1.71	0.76	0.45-1.06	5.64	-0.73-12.02	0.80	0.47-1.12
400	0.84	-0.10-1.79	0.74	0.42-1.06	5.90	-0.77-12.58	0.78	0.45-1.12
500	0.90	-0.09-1.89	0.72	0.39-1.06	6.27	-0.66-13.21	0.76	0.41-1.11
600	0.92	-0.07-1.92	0.72	0.38-1.05	6.38	-0.58-13.35	0.75	0.40-1.10
700	0.94	-0.06-1.94	0.71	0.37-1.05	6.45	-0.56-13.46	0.75	0.40-1.10
800	0.97	-0.03-1.96	0.70	0.36-1.04	6.64	-0.34-13.61	0.74	0.39-1.09
900	0.98	-0.03-1.96	0.70	0.36-1.03	6.67	-0.22-13.56	0.74	0.40-1.08
1000	0.99	0.01-1.97	0.69	0.36-1.02	6.74	-0.11-13.59	0.73	0.39-1.08

Figure S17. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of perennial herbaceous cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect evidence of functional responses in selection at any spatial scale.

Figure S18. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of perennial herbaceous cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect evidence of functional responses in use at any spatial scale.

Table S7. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of annual herbaceous cover around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results provide some evidence for decreasing use and selection of annual herbaceous cover with increasing availability. However, functional responses in selection are inconsistent across spatial scales, whereas functional responses in use are consistent at scales >100 m.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
100	0.05	-0.35-0.44	-0.48	-2.06-1.11	1.35	-0.22-2.93	-0.23	-1.58-1.13
200	0.02	-0.23-0.27	-0.13	-1.12-0.85	1.00	0.00-2.00	0.05	-0.81-0.90
300	-0.03	-0.27-0.21	0.29	-0.59-1.18	0.72	-0.02-1.46	0.27	-0.32-0.86
400	-0.06	-0.27-0.16	0.48	-0.25-1.21	0.64	-0.01-1.29	0.34	-0.16-0.84
500	-0.05	-0.23-0.14	0.52	-0.10-1.14	0.62	0.03-1.20	0.37	-0.07-0.82
600	-0.02	-0.20-0.15	0.50	-0.09-1.08	0.62	0.06-1.19	0.38	-0.06-0.82
700	0.01	-0.15-0.17	0.41	-0.15-0.97	0.69	0.13-1.24	0.34	-0.09-0.78
800	0.05	-0.09-0.20	0.31	-0.17-0.80	0.78	0.28-1.28	0.28	-0.11-0.67
900	0.07	-0.07-0.21	0.27	-0.18-0.72	0.83	0.36-1.31	0.25	-0.12-0.62
1000	0.10	-0.04-0.23	0.21	-0.21-0.63	0.92	0.47-1.36	0.20	-0.15-0.54

Figure S19. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of annual herbaceous cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis demonstrated some evidence for decreasing and tradeoff selection of annual herbaceous cover with increased availability, yet statistical significance of results were not consistent among spatial scales (Table S7).

Figure S20. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of annual herbaceous cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrated some evidence for tradeoff use of annual herbaceous cover with increased availability that was consistent across spatial scales.

Table S8. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of litter cover around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results show relaxed use and selection of litter cover, with strongest use and selection at low availability that approaches proportionality at high availability. These functional response results are also consistent across observational scales.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
100	1.80	1.20-2.41	0.43	0.23-0.63	12.66	8.05-17.27	0.46	0.23-0.68
200	1.76	1.15-2.37	0.44	0.24-0.64	12.35	7.79-16.91	0.47	0.24-0.69
300	1.75	1.10-2.39	0.44	0.23-0.66	12.29	7.50-17.07	0.47	0.23-0.71
400	1.74	1.10-2.38	0.45	0.23-0.66	12.24	7.47-17.00	0.47	0.24-0.71
500	1.73	1.10-2.36	0.45	0.24-0.66	12.18	7.49-16.87	0.47	0.24-0.70
600	1.71	1.09-2.33	0.46	0.25-0.66	12.00	7.34-16.66	0.48	0.25-0.72
700	1.69	1.07-2.31	0.46	0.25-0.67	11.87	7.23-16.51	0.49	0.26-0.72
800	1.68	1.07-2.29	0.47	0.26-0.67	11.74	7.16-16.33	0.49	0.27-0.72
900	1.68	1.07-2.29	0.47	0.26-0.67	11.72	7.15-16.29	0.50	0.27-0.72
1000	1.69	1.08-2.30	0.46	0.26-0.67	11.76	7.15-16.36	0.49	0.27-0.72

Figure S21. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of litter cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrated evidence for relaxed selection of litter cover with increased availability, and these results were consistent across spatial scales.

Figure S22. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of litter cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrated evidence for disproportionate use of more litter cover at low availability (approximately < 20% cover) that approaches proportional use of litter cover with increased availability. These results were consistent across spatial scales.

Table S9. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of bare ground around nest sites over a range of observational scales. These results failed to detect evidence of a functional response in selection, but decreased use of bare ground with increasing availability that was consistent across spatial scales.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
100	0.44	-0.79-1.66	0.84	0.50-1.17	6.55	-6.16-19.25	0.68	0.37-0.99
200	0.53	-0.66-1.72	0.81	0.49-1.14	7.21	-5.93-20.36	0.67	0.35-0.99
300	0.61	-0.59-1.81	0.79	0.46-1.12	7.92	-5.37-21.21	0.66	0.33-0.98
400	0.65	-0.54-1.84	0.78	0.45-1.11	8.25	-4.86-21.37	0.65	0.33-0.97
500	0.66	-0.53-1.85	0.78	0.45-1.11	8.18	-4.92-21.28	0.65	0.33-0.97
600	0.65	-0.53-1.83	0.78	0.46-1.11	8.01	-5.11-21.13	0.66	0.34-0.98
700	0.64	-0.52-1.80	0.78	0.46-1.10	7.88	-5.13-20.88	0.66	0.35-0.98
800	0.64	-0.50-1.78	0.79	0.47-1.10	7.89	-4.90-20.68	0.66	0.35-0.97
900	0.65	-0.48-1.77	0.78	0.47-1.09	7.99	-4.69-20.67	0.66	0.36-0.97
1000	0.65	-0.48-1.78	0.78	0.47-1.09	8.13	-4.57-20.83	0.66	0.35-0.97

Figure S23. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of bare ground by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect evidence of functional responses in selection of bare ground at any spatial scale.

Figure S24. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of bare ground by nesting greater sage-grouse, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrated consistent evidence for decreasing use of bare ground across spatial scales.

Table S10. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in use and selection of transect-scale herbaceous cover variables measured around nest sites. These results show: no evidence of functional responses to perennial grass cover, tradeoff functional responses in selection and use of perennial grass height, relaxed selection and use of perennial forb height and forb cover, no evidence of functional responses to forb richness, and mixed responses to annual grass cover.

Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Perennial grass cover	-0.80	-2.78-1.18	1.20	0.65-1.75	-8.92	-28.09-10.25	1.18	0.67-1.70
Perennial grass height	3.04	1.49-4.59	0.13	-0.30-0.57	27.79	11.76-43.83	0.17	-0.27-0.60
Perennial forb height	1.70	0.46-2.95	0.42	-0.01-0.85	9.45	1.90-17.00	0.50	0.09-0.90
Forb cover	1.83	0.95-2.70	0.37	0.05-0.70	8.77	3.03-14.52	0.55	0.19-0.92
Forb richness	0.27	-0.07-0.61	0.95	0.80-1.10	0.17	-1.72-2.07	1.16	1.03-1.30
Annual grass cover	0.77	-0.47-2.00	0.51	-0.06-1.08	4.78	1.22-8.33	0.24	0.01-0.48

Figure S25. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of perennial grass cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect a functional response by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S26. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of perennial grass cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect a functional response by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S27. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of perennial grass height by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates a tradeoff functional response in selection by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S28. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of perennial grass height by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates a tradeoff functional response in use by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S29. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of perennial forb height by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates a relaxed selection functional response in selection by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S30. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of perennial forb height by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates disproportionate use of perennial forb height by nesting greater sage-grouse at low availabilities that is relaxed at higher availabilities.

Figure S31. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of forb cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates a relaxed selection by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S32. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of forb cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure demonstrates a disproportionate use of forb cover by nesting greater sage-grouse at low availabilities that is relaxed as availability increases.

Figure S33. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of forb richness by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect a functional response in selection by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S34. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of forb richness by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect a functional response in use by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S35. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of annual grass cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect a functional response in selection by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Figure S36. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in selection of annual grass cover by nesting greater sage-grouse, measured along transects around nest sites. The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis suggested a tradeoff in use of annual grass cover by nesting greater sage-grouse.

Table S11. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of sagebrush cover during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results fail to provide evidence of functional responses during brood rearing.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	-0.01	-0.07-0.04	1.00	0.99-1.02	0.51	-0.5-1.59	0.97	0.92-1.02
200	-0.01	-0.05-0.04	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.43	-0.54-1.39	0.98	0.90-1.02
300	0.00	-0.04-0.04	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.51	-0.41-1.42	0.98	0.94-1.02
400	0.00	-0.04-0.04	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.56	-0.32-1.43	0.98	0.94-1.02
500	0.00	-0.04-0.04	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.61	-0.22-1.43	0.98	0.94-1.02
600	0.01	-0.03-0.04	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.64	-0.14-1.41	0.98	0.94-1.01
700	0.01	-0.02-0.04	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.66	-0.08-1.39	0.98	0.94-1.01
800	0.01	-0.02-0.05	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.68	0.01-1.35	0.98	0.95-1.01
900	0.02	-0.01-0.05	1.00	0.99-1.01	0.69	0.06-1.33	0.98	0.95-1.01
1000	0.02	-0.01-0.05	1.00	0.99-0.01	0.69	0.09-1.29	0.98	0.95-1.01
Late brood								
100	-1.68	-4.60-1.25	1.55	0.49-2.62	4.04	2.10-5.99	0.90	0.80-1.00
200	-1.70	-4.63-1.22	1.57	0.51-2.63	3.99	2.04-5.95	0.91	0.81-1.01
300	-1.71	-4.63-1.21	1.57	0.51-2.63	3.98	2.03-5.93	0.91	0.81-1.01
400	-1.71	-4.63-1.21	1.57	0.51-2.63	3.95	2.01-5.89	0.91	0.81-1.01
500	-1.71	-4.63-1.21	1.57	0.51-2.63	3.90	1.99-5.81	0.92	0.82-1.01
600	-1.71	-4.63-1.21	1.57	0.51-2.63	3.83	1.95-5.71	0.92	0.82-1.01
700	-1.72	-4.64-1.20	1.57	0.51-2.63	3.72	1.88-5.57	0.92	0.83-1.02
800	-1.73	-4.65-1.19	1.57	0.52-2.63	3.57	1.78-5.37	0.93	0.84-1.02
900	-1.74	-4.66-1.18	1.58	0.52-2.64	3.46	1.71-5.22	0.93	0.84-1.02
1000	-1.74	-4.66-1.17	1.58	0.52-2.64	3.37	1.65-5.08	0.94	0.85-1.02

Figure S37. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S38. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S39. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S40. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use of sagebrush cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S12. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of total shrub cover during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results failed to provide evidence of functional responses during brood rearing.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	-0.02	-0.18-0.14	1.00	0.95-1.05	0.17	-1.04-1.38	0.98	0.94-1.02
200	0.00	-0.15-0.15	1.00	0.95-1.05	0.29	-0.89-1.46	0.98	0.94-1.02
300	0.02	-0.13-0.16	0.99	0.95-1.04	0.45	-0.67-1.57	0.98	0.94-1.02
400	0.04	-0.10-0.18	0.99	0.94-1.03	0.55	-0.52-1.62	0.98	0.94-1.02
500	0.06	-0.07-0.19	0.98	0.94-1.02	0.65	-0.37-1.66	0.98	0.94-1.01
600	0.08	-0.04-0.21	0.98	0.94-1.02	0.78	-0.16-1.72	0.97	0.94-1.01
700	0.10	-0.02-0.21	0.97	0.93-1.01	0.87	-0.02-1.75	0.97	0.94-1.00
800	0.11	0.00-0.22	0.97	0.93-1.00	0.93	0.09-1.77	0.97	0.94-1.00
900	-0.05	-0.24-0.14	1.01	0.94-1.07	0.08	-1.34-1.51	0.97	0.92-1.03
1000	-0.03	-0.20-0.13	1.00	0.95-1.06	0.04	-1.24-1.32	0.98	0.93-1.03
Late brood								
100	0.06	-0.41-0.53	1.01	0.85-1.16	4.06	1.58-6.53	0.93	0.83-1.02
200	0.07	-0.40-0.53	1.01	0.85-1.16	4.09	1.63-6.55	0.93	0.83-1.02
300	0.07	-0.39-0.54	1.01	0.85-1.16	4.13	1.70-6.56	0.93	0.83-1.02
400	0.08	-0.38-0.54	1.00	0.85-1.15	4.14	1.73-6.55	0.93	0.83-1.02
500	0.08	-0.37-0.54	1.00	0.85-1.15	4.12	1.74-6.49	0.93	0.83-1.02
600	0.09	-0.36-0.54	1.00	0.85-1.15	4.07	1.75-6.39	0.93	0.84-1.02
700	0.09	-0.35-0.53	1.00	0.85-1.14	4.03	1.75-6.31	0.93	0.84-1.02
800	0.09	-0.34-0.53	1.00	0.85-1.14	3.98	1.74-6.22	0.93	0.84-1.02
900	0.07	-0.41-0.55	1.00	0.84-1.16	4.00	1.50-6.50	0.92	0.82-1.02
1000	0.06	-0.41-0.53	1.01	0.85-1.16	4.03	1.54-6.52	0.92	0.83-1.02

Figure S41. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of total shrub cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S42. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of total shrub cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use of shrub cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S43. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of total shrub cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection of shrub cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S44. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of total shrub cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use of shrub cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S13. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of Simpson's diversity index of sagebrush cover classes during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results failed to provide evidence of functional responses during brood rearing.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	-0.14	-0.39-0.11	1.01	0.93-1.09	0.00	-0.04-0.04	1.06	0.89-1.23
200	-0.10	-0.27-0.07	1.01	0.95-1.06	0.00	-0.05-0.04	1.04	0.90-1.18
300	-0.08	-0.22-0.06	1.00	0.96-1.05	0.00	-0.04-1.04	1.02	0.90-1.15
400	-0.07	-0.20-0.06	1.00	0.96-1.05	0.00	-0.04-0.04	1.01	0.90-1.12
500	-0.05	-0.16-0.06	1.00	0.96-1.04	0.00	-0.03-0.04	1.00	0.90-1.10
600	-0.04	-0.14-0.06	1.00	0.97-1.03	0.00	-0.03-0.04	1.00	0.91-1.09
700	-0.03	-0.12-0.06	1.00	0.97-1.03	0.00	-0.03-0.03	1.00	0.91-1.09
800	-0.04	-0.12-0.05	1.00	0.97-1.03	0.00	-0.03-0.03	1.01	0.93-1.09
900	-0.04	-0.12-0.04	1.00	0.97-1.03	0.00	-0.03-0.02	1.01	0.93-1.08
1000	-0.04	-0.12-0.03	1.00	0.98-1.03	-0.01	-0.04-0.02	1.01	0.94-1.08
Late brood								
100	0.20	-0.46-0.86	1.18	0.78-1.58	0.03	-0.04-0.11	0.95	0.65-1.24
200	0.23	-0.43-0.90	1.28	0.82-1.74	0.02	-0.06-0.10	0.98	0.70-1.25
300	0.23	-0.34-0.81	1.29	0.87-1.71	0.02	-0.07-0.10	0.98	0.71-1.24
400	0.23	-0.31-0.76	1.29	0.88-1.69	0.02	-0.07-0.10	0.98	0.72-1.23
500	0.22	-0.27-0.71	1.28	0.90-1.67	0.01	-0.07-0.10	0.98	0.73-1.23
600	0.21	-0.25-0.67	1.27	0.90-1.64	0.01	-0.07-0.10	0.98	0.73-1.23
700	0.22	-0.23-0.66	1.28	0.92-1.64	0.01	-0.08-0.10	0.99	0.74-1.24
800	0.23	-0.19-0.66	1.30	0.94-1.66	0.01	-0.08-0.10	1.00	0.76-1.24
900	0.25	-0.16-0.66	1.31	0.96-1.67	0.01	-0.08-0.10	1.01	0.76-1.25
1000	0.26	-0.14-0.7	1.32	0.97-1.68	0.01	-0.09-0.10	1.01	0.77-1.25

Figure S45. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of Simpson's diversity index of sagebrush cover classes by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S46. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of Simpson's diversity index of sagebrush cover classes by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S47. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of Simpson's diversity index of sagebrush cover classes by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S48. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of Simpson's diversity index of sagebrush cover classes by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S14. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of sagebrush height during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use, and weak evidence for functional responses in selection at some scales (during early brood rearing only).

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	-0.27	-0.56-0.02	1.07	0.99-1.16	-0.15	-2.68-2.39	1.01	0.95-1.07
200	-0.30	-0.56 - -0.04	1.08	1.01-1.16	-0.23	-2.54-2.07	1.01	0.96-1.07
300	-0.29	-0.54 - -0.04	1.08	1.01-1.15	0.07	-2.12-2.25	1.01	0.96-1.06
400	-0.27	-0.50 - -0.03	1.08	1.01-1.14	0.27	-1.81-2.36	1.01	0.96-1.06
500	-0.25	-0.47 - -0.03	1.07	1.01-1.14	0.46	-1.52-2.44	1.00	0.96-1.05
600	-0.23	-0.44 - -0.02	1.07	1.01-1.13	0.58	-1.33-2.50	1.00	0.96-1.05
700	-0.20	-0.39-0.00	1.06	1.00-1.11	0.70	-1.17-2.57	1.00	0.96-1.05
800	-0.16	-0.34-0.02	1.05	1.00-1.10	0.80	-1.00-2.60	1.00	0.95-1.04
900	-0.14	-0.31-0.03	1.04	1.00-1.09	0.84	-0.90-2.59	1.00	0.95-1.04
1000	-0.12	-0.28-0.04	1.04	0.99-1.08	0.85	-0.84-2.54	1.00	0.96-1.04
Late brood								
100	0.32	-0.15-0.79	0.93	0.80-1.07	6.33	2.47-10.19	0.92	0.82-1.02
200	0.27	-0.19-0.73	0.95	0.82-1.08	6.09	2.30-9.88	0.93	0.83-1.03
300	0.29	-0.17-0.74	0.95	0.81-1.08	6.06	2.29-9.83	0.93	0.83-1.03
400	0.30	-0.14-0.75	0.94	0.81-1.07	6.03	2.29-9.76	0.93	0.83-1.03
500	0.33	-0.10-0.76	0.93	0.81-1.06	5.95	2.27-9.62	0.93	0.84-1.03
600	0.33	-0.09-0.76	0.93	0.81-1.05	5.83	2.21-9.45	0.93	0.84-1.03
700	0.33	-0.08-0.74	0.93	0.81-1.05	5.64	2.08-9.20	0.94	0.84-1.03
800	0.31	-0.08-0.71	0.94	0.82-1.05	5.36	1.91-8.80	0.94	0.85-1.03
900	0.31	-0.07-0.69	0.94	0.83-1.05	5.18	1.83-8.54	0.94	0.86-1.03
1000	0.31	-0.07-0.68	0.94	0.83-1.04	5.01	1.75-8.27	0.95	0.86-1.03

Figure S49. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush height by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis provided weak evidence of functional responses in selection at some spatial scales (200-600 m) by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period (Table S14).

Figure S50. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of sagebrush height by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use of sagebrush height by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S51. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of sagebrush height by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection of sagebrush height by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S52. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of sagebrush height by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use of sagebrush height by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S15. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of total herbaceous cover during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results failed to provide evidence of functional responses during brood rearing.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	-0.02	-0.33-0.29	1.01	0.91-1.11	0.45	-2.00-2.90	0.98	0.88-1.09
200	-0.08	-0.37-0.21	1.02	0.93-1.12	0.13	-2.17-2.43	1.00	0.90-1.10
300	-0.09	-0.36-0.18	1.03	0.94-1.12	-0.06	-2.20-2.07	1.01	0.91-1.10
400	-0.11	-0.36-0.15	1.03	0.95-1.12	-0.26	-2.27-1.75	1.01	0.93-1.10
500	-0.12	-0.35-0.11	1.04	0.96-1.11	-0.43	-2.28-1.41	1.02	0.94-1.10
600	-0.12	-0.34-0.09	1.04	0.97-1.11	-0.52	-2.23-1.20	1.03	0.95-1.10
700	-0.12	-0.32-0.08	1.04	0.97-1.10	-0.54	-2.14-1.06	1.03	0.96-1.10
800	-0.12	-0.30-0.06	1.04	0.98-1.10	-0.57	-2.03-0.90	1.03	0.97-1.09
900	-0.12	-0.28-0.05	1.04	0.98-1.09	-0.58	-1.95-0.80	1.03	0.97-1.09
1000	-0.11	-0.26-0.04	1.04	0.99-1.09	-0.57	-1.86-0.72	1.03	0.98-1.09
Late brood								
100	0.39	-0.15-0.92	0.89	0.71-1.06	2.37	-1.87-6.62	0.94	0.76-1.12
200	0.35	-0.19-0.89	0.90	0.73-1.07	2.16	-2.05-6.37	0.95	0.77-1.13
300	0.33	-0.20-0.86	0.90	0.73-1.07	2.00	-2.16-6.15	0.95	0.78-1.13
400	0.32	-0.20-0.84	0.91	0.74-1.08	1.86	-2.22-5.93	0.96	0.79-1.13
500	0.31	-0.20-0.81	0.91	0.75-1.07	1.73	-2.23-5.68	0.96	0.79-1.13
600	0.30	-0.20-0.79	0.91	0.75-1.07	1.61	-2.24-5.46	0.97	0.80-1.13
700	0.29	-0.20-0.77	0.92	0.76-1.07	1.49	-2.25-5.22	0.97	0.81-1.13
800	0.28	-0.19-0.75	0.92	0.77-1.07	1.36	-2.23-4.95	0.98	0.82-1.13
900	0.28	-0.17-0.74	0.92	0.77-1.06	1.33	-2.16-4.82	0.98	0.83-1.12
1000	0.28	-0.16-0.73	0.92	0.78-1.06	1.29	-2.10-4.67	0.98	0.83-1.12

Figure S53. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of total herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S54. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of total herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S55. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of total herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S56. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of total herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100–1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100–500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600–1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S16. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of perennial herbaceous cover during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results failed to provide evidence of functional responses during brood rearing.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	0.00	-0.29-0.29	1.00	0.91-1.10	0.42	-1.77-2.62	0.99	0.89-1.09
200	-0.08	-0.35-0.19	1.03	0.94-1.12	0.19	-1.87-2.25	1.00	0.90-1.09
300	-0.08	-0.33-0.16	1.03	0.95-1.11	0.10	-1.83-2.02	1.00	0.92-1.09
400	-0.08	-0.31-0.15	1.03	0.95-1.10	-0.03	-1.84-1.78	1.01	0.93-1.09
500	-0.08	-0.29-0.13	1.03	0.96-1.10	-0.16	-1.81-1.49	1.02	0.94-1.09
600	-0.08	-0.27-0.11	1.03	0.97-1.09	-0.26	-1.78-1.25	1.02	0.95-1.09
700	-0.08	-0.26-0.09	1.03	0.97-1.09	-0.32	-1.72-1.08	1.02	0.97-1.09
800	-0.09	-0.24-0.06	1.03	0.98-1.08	-0.40	-1.65-0.86	1.03	0.97-1.08
900	-0.09	-0.23-0.05	1.03	0.99-1.08	-0.44	-1.60-0.73	1.03	0.98-1.08
1000	-0.09	-0.22-0.04	1.03	0.99-1.07	-0.45	-1.54-0.64	1.03	0.98-1.08
Late brood								
100	0.46	-0.07-0.98	0.87	0.70-1.04	2.73	-1.16-6.63	0.93	0.76-1.11
200	0.41	-0.10-0.93	0.88	0.71-1.05	2.52	-1.33-6.37	0.94	0.76-1.11
300	0.40	-0.10-0.90	0.88	0.72-1.05	2.41	-1.37-6.20	0.94	0.77-1.11
400	0.39	-0.10-0.88	0.89	0.72-1.05	2.32	-1.39-6.02	0.95	0.78-1.11
500	0.39	-0.09-0.86	0.89	0.73-1.04	2.19	-1.39-5.78	0.95	0.79-1.11
600	0.38	-0.08-0.84	0.89	0.74-1.04	2.08	-1.40-5.75	0.95	0.80-1.11
700	0.37	-0.08-0.82	0.89	0.74-1.04	1.97	-1.42-5.35	0.96	0.80-1.11
800	0.36	-0.08-0.80	0.89	0.75-1.04	1.84	-1.42-5.09	0.96	0.81-1.11
900	0.37	-0.06-0.79	0.89	0.75-1.03	1.79	-1.37-4.96	0.96	0.82-1.10
1000	0.37	-0.05-0.78	0.89	0.76-1.03	1.74	-1.34-4.82	0.96	0.82-1.10

Figure S57. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of perennial herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S58. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of perennial herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S59. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of perennial herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S60. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of perennial herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S17. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of annual herbaceous cover during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results provide evidence of relaxed avoidance for both selection and use during early brood rearing but failed to provide evidence of functional responses during late brood rearing.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	-0.62	-0.89 - -0.36	1.40	1.12-1.67	-0.40	-0.84-0.03	1.28	1.02-1.54
200	-0.61	-0.86 - -0.35	1.42	1.17-1.66	-0.42	-0.76 - -0.07	1.27	1.06-1.49
300	-0.54	-0.77 - -0.32	1.40	1.18-1.62	-0.43	-0.74 - -0.13	1.28	1.09-1.46
400	-0.49	-0.69 - -0.28	1.38	1.18-1.57	-0.43	-0.71 - -0.15	1.27	1.10-1.44
500	-0.41	-0.59 - -0.24	1.28	1.11-1.45	-0.41	-0.67 - -0.16	1.25	1.09-1.41
600	-0.36	-0.51 - -0.20	1.23	1.08-1.38	-0.40	-0.64 - -0.16	1.25	1.10-1.39
700	-0.31	-0.45 - -0.17	1.21	1.07-1.35	-0.38	-0.60 - -0.15	1.24	1.10-1.37
800	-0.26	-0.39 - -0.14	1.19	1.07-1.31	-0.35	-0.56 - -0.14	1.23	1.10-1.36
900	-0.23	-0.35 - -0.12	1.18	1.06-1.30	-0.32	-0.52 - -0.12	1.21	1.09-1.34
1000	-0.21	-0.31 - -0.10	1.17	1.06-1.27	-0.29	-0.48 - -0.10	1.20	1.08-1.31
Late brood								
100	-0.50	-0.76 - -0.24	0.84	0.47-1.21	-0.11	-0.62-0.40	0.96	0.60-1.32
200	-0.57	-0.88 - -0.27	0.90	0.46-1.34	-0.12	-0.61-0.37	0.94	0.60-1.29
300	-0.63	-0.96 - -0.30	1.22	0.77-1.68	-0.13	-0.59-0.34	0.94	0.61-1.27
400	-0.60	-0.91 - -0.29	1.21	0.78-1.64	-0.14	-0.60-0.32	0.95	0.62-1.27
500	-0.56	-0.84 - -0.27	1.19	0.79-1.59	-0.15	-0.60-0.30	0.97	0.65-1.29
600	-0.52	-0.80 - -0.24	1.19	0.80-1.59	-0.16	-0.60-0.29	0.98	0.66-1.29
700	-0.49	-0.75 - -0.22	1.18	0.81-1.55	-0.16	-0.59-0.27	0.99	0.68-1.29
800	-0.43	-0.67 - -0.20	1.09	0.75-1.43	-0.15	-0.57-0.27	0.99	0.69-0.28
900	-0.40	-0.63 - -0.18	1.04	0.73-1.36	-0.15	-0.56-0.26	0.99	0.70-1.27
1000	-0.38	-0.59 - -0.16	1.01	0.71-1.31	-0.14	-0.54-0.26	0.98	0.70-1.26

Figure S61. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of annual herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure provides evidence of relaxed avoidance in selection by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S62. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of annual herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure provides evidence of relaxed avoidance in use by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S63. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of annual herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S64. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of annual herbaceous cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S18. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of litter cover during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection and use during early brood rearing but provide evidence of relaxed selection and use during late brood rearing by greater sage-grouse.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	0.25	-0.02-0.52	0.92	0.83-1.01	1.50	-0.49-3.49	0.93	0.84-1.02
200	0.18	-0.07-0.42	0.94	0.86-1.02	1.02	-0.79-2.83	0.96	0.87-1.04
300	0.14	-0.08-0.37	0.95	0.88-1.03	0.86	-0.79-2.51	0.96	0.89-1.04
400	0.12	-0.09-0.33	0.96	0.89-1.03	0.73	-0.80-2.26	0.97	0.90-1.04
500	0.08	-0.11-0.27	0.97	0.91-1.04	0.52	-0.87-1.91	0.98	0.92-1.04
600	0.06	-0.12-0.24	0.98	0.92-1.04	0.41	-0.89-1.71	0.99	0.93-1.04
700	0.05	-0.12-0.22	0.98	0.93-1.04	0.34	-0.87-1.55	0.99	0.93-1.04
800	0.04	-0.11-0.19	0.99	0.94-1.04	0.26	-0.84-1.35	0.99	0.94-1.04
900	0.03	-0.11-0.17	0.99	0.95-1.04	0.19	-0.83-1.22	1.00	0.95-1.04
1000	0.02	-0.11-0.15	0.99	0.95-1.04	0.13	-0.83-1.09	1.00	0.96-1.04
Late brood								
100	0.99	0.47-1.52	0.69	0.52-0.87	7.22	3.35-11.09	0.72	0.54-0.90
200	0.93	0.41-1.45	0.71	0.54-0.89	6.94	3.09-10.79	0.74	0.56-0.92
300	0.92	0.40-1.44	0.72	0.55-0.89	6.92	3.11-10.73	0.74	0.56-0.91
400	0.92	0.41-1.43	0.72	0.55-0.88	6.91	3.16-10.66	0.73	0.56-0.91
500	0.91	0.41-1.40	0.72	0.56-0.88	6.81	3.14-10.47	0.74	0.57-0.91
600	0.89	0.40-1.37	0.73	0.57-0.89	6.67	3.07-10.26	0.74	0.58-0.91
700	0.86	0.39-1.34	0.73	0.58-0.89	6.48	2.95-10.01	0.75	0.59-0.91
800	0.83	0.37-1.29	0.74	0.59-0.90	6.20	2.77-9.63	0.76	0.60-0.92
900	0.81	0.36-1.27	0.75	0.60-0.90	6.05	2.70-9.40	0.77	0.61-0.92
1000	0.80	0.36-1.24	0.75	0.61-0.90	5.93	2.64-9.21	0.77	0.62-0.92

Figure S65. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of litter cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S66. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of litter cover by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to provide evidence of functional responses in use by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S67. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of litter cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure provides evidence of relaxed selection by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S68. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of litter cover by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure provides evidence of relaxed use by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Table S19. Results of type 1 (additive scale) and type 2 (log scale) regression analyses testing for functional responses in greater sage-grouse use and selection of bare ground during early and late brood rearing, with cover measured over a range of observational scales. These results provide weak evidence of functional responses in use at some scales but not selection during early brood rearing, and evidence of decreasing selection and use during late brood rearing.

Period and Observational scale (m)	Log scale (selection)				Additive scale (use)			
	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI	B ₀	95% CI	B ₁	95% CI
Early brood								
100	0.22	0.04-0.40	0.94	0.88-0.99	1.98	-0.02-3.98	0.93	0.88-0.99
200	0.17	0.00-0.33	0.95	0.90-1.00	1.51	-0.28-3.31	0.94	0.90-0.99
300	0.14	-0.02-0.29	0.96	0.91-1.00	1.27	-0.40-2.95	0.95	0.90-0.99
400	0.11	-0.04-0.26	0.96	0.92-1.01	1.08	-0.54-2.70	0.95	0.91-0.99
500	0.08	-0.06-0.23	0.97	0.93-1.01	0.91	-0.69-2.50	0.95	0.91-0.99
600	0.07	-0.07-0.22	0.97	0.93-1.02	0.82	-0.76-2.39	0.95	0.91-1.00
700	0.07	-0.09-0.21	0.97	0.93-1.02	0.75	-0.80-2.31	0.95	0.91-1.00
800	0.07	-0.07-0.20	0.97	0.93-1.01	0.67	-0.84-2.18	0.95	0.91-1.00
900	0.07	-0.06-0.20	0.97	0.93-1.01	0.60	-0.87-2.07	0.96	0.92-0.99
1000	0.07	-0.06-0.20	0.97	0.93-1.01	0.54	-0.89-1.97	0.96	0.92-0.99
Late brood								
100	0.35	-0.05-0.74	0.85	0.74-0.96	2.44	-1.78-6.65	0.77	0.66-0.87
200	0.31	-0.08-0.71	0.86	0.75-0.97	2.03	-2.15-6.21	0.78	0.67-0.88
300	0.29	-0.11-0.68	0.86	0.75-0.98	1.76	-2.38-5.91	0.78	0.68-0.88
400	0.27	-0.12-0.66	0.87	0.76-0.98	1.58	-2.52-5.68	0.78	0.68-0.89
500	0.25	-0.14-0.66	0.87	0.77-0.98	1.39	-2.63-5.41	0.79	0.69-0.89
600	0.23	-0.15-0.61	0.88	0.77-0.99	1.26	-2.69-5.21	0.79	0.69-0.89
700	0.21	-0.16-0.59	0.88	0.78-0.99	1.15	-2.74-5.04	0.80	0.70-0.89
800	0.20	-0.16-0.56	0.89	0.79-0.99	1.07	-2.72-4.86	0.80	0.71-0.90
900	0.19	-0.16-0.54	0.89	0.79-0.99	1.02	-2.70-4.75	0.81	0.71-0.90
1000	0.18	-0.16-0.53	0.90	0.80-0.99	0.99	-2.67-4.64	0.81	0.72-0.90

Figure S69. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of bare ground by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This analysis failed to detect functional responses in selection by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period.

Figure S70. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of bare ground by greater sage-grouse during the early brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure provides weak evidence of decreasing use of bare ground at some scales during the early brood period.

Figure S71. Plot of log of mean cover at use sites against log of mean cover that was available from type 2 analyses of functional responses in selection of bare ground by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure provides evidence of decreasing selection by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Figure S72. Plot of mean cover at use sites against mean cover that was available from type 1 analyses of functional responses in use of bare ground by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period, replicated across spatial scales of 100-1000 m around nest sites (top from left to right: 100-500 m by 100-m increments; bottom from left to right: 600-1000 m by 100-m increments). The fitted regression line is shown in solid black, whereas the dashed line is the 1:1 line expected under proportional use (i.e., no selection). This figure provides evidence of decreasing use by greater sage-grouse during the late brood period.

Additional results for generalized resource selection function modeling to predict breeding-season space use of greater sage-grouse in response to catastrophic wildfire.

Figure S73. Partial effects plots for covariates in optimally-predictive resource selection function for nest site selection by greater sage-grouse. Variables shown are those lacking functional responses in the final model: A) annual herbaceous cover, B) perennial grass cover, C) perennial forb height, D) forb cover, E) forb richness, F) compound topographic index (CTI), G) site exposure, H) distance to the closest mesic patch, and I) distance to the nearest known lek. The z-axis (w) represents the predicted relative intensity of use.

A)

B)

C)

D)

E)

F)

G)

H)

D)

Table S20. Optimizing the scale and shape of the sagebrush cover variable for predicting nest site selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Aavail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Aavail}$	$\beta^2 \times \text{Aavail}$	AUC
100	0.307	-	-0.540	-	0.646
200	0.275	-	-0.404	-	0.641
300	0.289	-	-0.473	-	0.642
400	0.297	-0.003	-0.530	-	0.639
500	0.300	-0.026	-0.548	-	0.638
600	0.300	-0.028	-0.544	-	0.637
700	0.298	-0.016	-0.518	-	0.638
800	0.306	-0.017	-0.536	-	0.639
900	0.300	-	-0.489	-	0.639
1000	0.302	-	-0.491	-	0.640

Table S21. Optimizing the scale and shape of the Simpson's diversity index for sagebrush cover categories variable for predicting nest site selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Aavail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Aavail}$	AUC
100	0.014	0.005	-0.230	0.516
200	-	-	-0.473	0.562
300	-	-0.050	-0.598	0.565
400	-0.012	-0.098	-0.753	0.562
500	-	-0.094	-0.555	0.558
600	-	-0.130	-0.658	0.563
700	-	-0.139	-0.648	0.566
800	-0.013	-0.124	-0.683	0.567
900	-0.015	-0.106	-0.660	0.569
1000	-0.010	-0.095	-0.612	0.570

Table S22. Optimizing the scale and shape of the perennial herbaceous cover variable for predicting nest site selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.133	-0.106	-0.258	0.596
200	0.156	-0.117	-0.303	0.604
300	0.165	-0.092	-0.401	0.615
400	0.163	-0.074	-0.460	0.620
500	0.158	-0.067	-0.488	0.624
600	0.160	-0.062	-0.510	0.622
700	0.160	-0.058	-0.524	0.619
800	0.159	-0.056	-0.533	0.620
900	0.169	-0.063	-0.554	0.618
1000	0.172	-0.059	-0.571	0.618

Table S23. Optimizing the scale and shape of the annual herbaceous cover variable for predicting nest site selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	-0.011	-	0.498
200	-0.010	-	0.502
300	-0.016	-	0.507
400	-0.027	-	0.510
500	-0.016	-	0.507
600	-0.011	-	0.496
700	-	-	0.488
800	-0.001	-0.021	0.468
900	-	-	0.466
1000	-	-	0.487

Table S24. Optimizing the scale and shape of the litter cover variable for predicting nest site selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.107	-0.522	0.625
200	0.094	-0.532	0.631
300	0.093	-0.559	0.633
400	0.090	-0.568	0.634
500	0.092	-0.559	0.634
600	0.101	-0.555	0.630
700	0.107	-0.545	0.631
800	0.114	-0.539	0.632
900	0.122	-0.531	0.633
1000	0.125	-0.524	0.634

Table S25. Optimizing the scale and shape of the bare ground cover variable for predicting nest site selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	-0.233	-0.531	0.624
200	-0.235	-0.607	0.631
300	-0.211	-0.513	0.637
400	-0.236	-0.603	0.638
500	-0.252	-0.658	0.639
600	-0.233	-0.587	0.641
700	-0.237	-0.586	0.643
800	-0.264	-0.653	0.644
900	-0.249	-0.600	0.646
1000	-0.275	-0.673	0.647

Figure S74. Partial effects plots for covariates in optimally-predictive resource selection function for early brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. Variables shown are those lacking functional responses in the final model: A) litter cover, B) topographic roughness, C) compound topographic index (CTI), D) site exposure, E) distance to the closest mesic grass patch, and F) distance outside the fire boundary. The z-axis (w) represents the predicted relative intensity of use.

A)

B)

C)

D)

E)

F)

Table S26. Optimizing the scale and shape of the sagebrush cover variable for predicting early brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	$\beta^2 \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.054	-0.490	0.363	-0.075	0.547
200	0.110	-0.600	0.466	-0.099	0.545
300	0.148	-0.693	0.550	-0.116	0.544
400	0.109	-0.350	0.207	-0.088	0.544
500	0.135	-0.381	0.228	-0.101	0.548
600	0.150	-0.480	0.323	-0.110	0.552
700	0.152	-0.534	0.375	-0.109	0.556
800	0.155	-0.600	0.440	-0.109	0.560
900	0.165	-0.713	0.554	-0.113	0.562
1000	0.166	-0.743	0.587	-0.111	0.563

Table S27. Optimizing the scale and shape of the Simpson's diversity index for sagebrush cover categories variable for predicting early brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	$\beta^2 \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.022	-	-	-	0.515
200	-	-0.120	0.118	0.048	0.523
300	-	-0.196	0.194	0.039	0.528
400	-0.030	-0.261	0.256	0.052	0.531
500	-0.032	-0.386	0.376	0.046	0.546
600	-	-0.460	0.457	0.026	0.556
700	-	-0.527	0.536	0.029	0.563
800	-	-0.552	0.580	0.030	0.566
900	-	-0.539	0.574	0.028	0.563
1000	-	-0.416	0.447	0.022	0.557

Table S28. Optimizing the scale and shape of the perennial herbaceous cover variable for predicting early brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.014	-	0.026	0.528
200	0.019	-	0.026	0.530
300	0.022	-	0.026	0.529
400	0.020	-	0.026	0.530
500	0.020	-	0.028	0.529
600	0.025	-	0.035	0.529
700	0.028	-	0.039	0.528
800	0.029	-	0.041	0.526
900	-	0.010	-	0.525
1000	0.009	0.029	-	0.527

Table S29. Optimizing the scale and shape of the annual herbaceous cover variable for predicting early brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	-	0.002	-	0.505
200	-0.136	0.018	0.015	0.529
300	-0.167	0.002	0.051	0.545
400	-0.183	-	0.056	0.545
500	-0.035	-	0.010	0.545
600	-0.189	-	0.053	0.544
700	-0.176	-	0.049	0.542
800	-0.015	-	0.006	0.539
900	-0.015	-	0.007	0.534
1000	-0.021	-	0.008	0.530

Table S30. Optimizing the scale and shape of the litter cover variable for predicting early brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	-	-0.009	-	0.527
200	-	-0.008	-	0.531
300	-	-0.008	-	0.535
400	-	-0.008	-	0.534
500	-	-0.007	-	0.532
600	-	-0.009	-	0.529
700	-	-0.008	-	0.526
800	-	-0.007	-	0.523
900	-	-0.008	-	0.522
1000	-	-0.007	-	0.521

Table S31. Optimizing the scale and shape of the bare ground cover variable for predicting early brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	$\beta^2 \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.090	-0.613	0.528	-	0.572
200	0.054	-0.677	0.618	-0.005	0.563
300	0.057	-0.744	0.722	-0.030	0.561
400	0.064	-0.765	0.779	-0.051	0.556
500	0.064	-0.775	0.816	-0.063	0.548
600	-	-	-	-0.002	0.511
700	-	-	-	-0.002	0.513
800	-	-	-	-0.002	0.515
900	-	-	-	-0.002	0.516
1000	-	-	-	-0.002	0.516

Figure S75. Partial effects plots for covariates in optimally-predictive resource selection function for late brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. Variables shown are those lacking functional responses in the final model: A) perennial herbaceous cover, B) annual herbaceous cover, C) litter cover, D) topographic roughness, E) compound topographic index (CTI), F) site exposure, G) distance to the closest mesic grass patch, and H) distance outside the fire boundary. The z-axis (w) represents the predicted relative intensity of use. A)

B)

C)

D)

E)

F)

G)

H)

Table S32. Optimizing the scale and shape of the sagebrush cover variable for predicting late brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	$\beta^2 \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.625	-0.657	0.327	-0.431	0.617
200	0.681	-0.650	0.332	-0.457	0.617
300	0.712	-0.642	0.331	-0.470	0.615
400	0.648	-0.541	0.218	-0.407	0.615
500	0.754	-0.654	0.358	-0.487	0.614
600	0.766	-0.678	0.391	-0.491	0.615
700	0.773	-0.699	0.423	-0.492	0.614
800	0.776	-0.731	0.473	-0.490	0.614
900	0.777	-0.755	0.509	-0.487	0.614
1000	0.777	-0.774	0.541	-0.484	0.614

Table S33. Optimizing the scale and shape of the Simpson's diversity index for sagebrush cover categories variable for predicting late brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	$\beta^2 \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.146	-0.158	0.164	-0.136	0.543
200	0.141	-0.299	0.309	-0.182	0.557
300	0.158	-0.383	0.401	-0.240	0.567
400	0.164	-0.407	0.424	-0.266	0.568
500	0.168	-0.422	0.444	-0.282	0.571
600	0.170	-0.440	0.467	-0.284	0.575
700	0.173	-0.452	0.488	-0.288	0.577
800	0.187	-0.447	0.511	-0.298	0.577
900	0.201	-0.430	0.510	-0.305	0.575
1000	0.215	-0.407	0.499	-0.312	0.573

Table S34. Optimizing the scale and shape of the perennial herbaceous cover variable for predicting late brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.185	-0.032	-	0.563
200	0.180	-0.032	-	0.562
300	0.178	-0.027	-	0.560
400	0.174	-0.025	-	0.558
500	0.170	-0.023	-	0.556
600	0.168	-0.023	-	0.555
700	0.016	-	-	0.554
800	0.153	-0.022	-	0.551
900	0.148	-0.022	-	0.550
1000	0.145	-0.022	-	0.549

Table S35. Optimizing the scale and shape of the annual herbaceous cover variable for predicting late brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	-0.134	0.015	0.069	0.525
200	-0.185	0.033	0.035	0.531
300	-0.210	0.042	0.027	0.535
400	-0.224	0.046	0.028	0.538
500	-0.221	0.047	0.023	0.540
600	-0.207	0.046	0.016	0.540
700	-0.175	0.041	0.002	0.539
800	-0.161	0.037	0.003	0.537
900	-0.158	0.036	0.004	0.535
1000	-0.156	0.036	0.004	0.534

Table S36. Optimizing the scale and shape of the litter cover variable for predicting late brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	0.295	-0.005	-0.050	0.581
200	0.314	-	-0.028	0.583
300	0.315	-	-0.014	0.584
400	0.307	-	-	0.583
500	0.025	-	-	0.583
600	0.025	-	-	0.581
700	0.024	-	-	0.579
800	0.023	-	-	0.575
900	0.022	-	-	0.573
1000	0.022	-	-	0.571

Table S37. Optimizing the scale and shape of the bare ground cover variable for predicting late brood-rearing habitat selection by greater sage-grouse. A variable multiplied by the average value over the site-year combination (Avail) indicates a functional response.

Observational scale (m)	β	β^2	$\beta \times \text{Avail}$	$\beta^2 \times \text{Avail}$	AUC
100	-0.578	-0.628	-	0.475	0.632
200	-0.551	-0.520	-	0.388	0.634
300	-0.405	-0.318	-	0.226	0.635
400	-0.581	-0.466	-	0.355	0.635
500	-0.613	-0.470	-	0.360	0.634
600	-0.605	-0.449	-	0.342	0.634
700	-0.637	-0.475	-	0.360	0.633
800	-0.641	-0.477	-	0.358	0.633
900	-0.641	-0.476	-	0.355	0.632
1000	-0.619	-0.453	-	0.335	0.631